

PHILOSOPHICAL SCIENCES

ISLAM, JUDAISM AND CHRISTIANITY

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**Zhamashev A.,
Talasbayev E.**

Al-Farabi Kazakh National University. Kazakhstan, Almaty

Abstract

The Article is an attempt to investigate formation and interactions of Islam, Judaism and Christianity in diachronic view. During the past centuries the treatment of Islam based on Christian theological positions. Christian polemicists and theologians tried to approve that Islam was a heresy and its Prophet Muhammad was a liar.

In the 19-th century the scientific religious studies had grown up, but the principles of Islamic academic studies aimed to present the religious doctrine and the cult of Islam as borrowings from previous religions of Christianity and Judaism or more ancient religions.

Keywords: *Islam, Christianity, Judaism, autochthonous, dogma.*

The question of the relationship of Islam to Christianity and Judaism is one of the most sensitive aspects of interreligious relations in modern society, as well as an urgent problem in religious studies. Actively developing processes of globalization lead, on the one hand, to the penetration of Western culture and ideology into the regions of North Africa, the Middle East, and Southeast Asia, where Muslim peoples mostly live. On the other hand, an increasing number of Muslims from different countries of the East are settling in traditionally Christian Europe and America. According to the Department of Religion and Public Life of the American Pew Center, in Europe (excluding the population of Russia) in 2010 there were more than 43 million Muslims - about 7% of the total European population [20]. Turkey, where more than 70 million Muslims live, Russia - about 20 million Muslims, and Azerbaijan - 6 million Muslims, should also be mentioned here. These figures are growing from year to year, and the problem of the relationship of religions and their followers to each other will become more acute.

During the XX and at the beginning of the XXI century, the relations between Muslims and Jews became no less complicated, but rather dramatic and tragic. This happened as a result of the creation of the State of Israel in the Arab territories in 1948. In a dense environment of Arab states, including Egypt, Jordan, Syria and Lebanon, the overwhelming majority of whose population are Muslims, numerous representatives of Judaism began to live compactly in Israel - in 2013 their number was just over 6 million [21]. In addition, due to the unrestrained territorial expansion of Israel, which began in 1948 and continued until 1985, more than 2 million non-Jews now live on the territory of Israel itself, most of whom are Muslims (17% of the population of Israel). And although political and territorial conflicts create the main sharpness of contradictions between Arabs and Israelis, interfaith clashes between Jews and Muslims do not lose their intensity, an example of which is the dispute over the status of the Temple Mount, on which stands the third Muslim shrine after the Kaaba in Mecca and

the Mosque of the Prophet in Beijing - the Dome of the Rock Mosque.

A scientific analysis of the relationship between Islam and Christianity and Judaism requires an appeal to the origins of Islam as a religion younger and more recently formed, as well as a careful study of how Christianity and Judaism were represented in pre-Islamic Arabia.

In pre-Islamic Arabia, the followers of Christianity and Judaism left well-traced historical traces of their presence. For a number of researchers, the presence of these traces gave grounds to assert that many religious ideas and dogmas of Christianity and Judaism, which preceded Islam in time, formed the basis of the text of the Koran, influenced the formation of the Sunnah and even reflected on the essence of the creed and cult of Islam. Since these statements themselves do not have sufficient grounds and follow largely from the statements of Christian polemicists and atheist religious scholars of the past periods, it would be natural to turn once again to the pre-Islamic history of the Arabs, as well as carefully consider the historical evidence of the penetration of Christians and Jews into the Arab socio-cultural environment.

Turning first of all to Christianity, we must take into account that this religious tradition was formed initially as a heterogeneous teaching. From the earliest stage of its development, Christianity began to branch out into various interpretations and currents. That is why, in order to analyze the relations between Islam and Christianity in the seventh century, it is important to clearly understand what trends the latter had to face the Arabs as a whole, and the Prophet Muhammad, and the first Muslims at the time when the teachings of Islam were being formed.

Although much less is known about the diversification of the religious teachings of the Jews of that time, it is obvious that Judaism, which penetrated into different regions of Arabia, had its own characteristics.

If we try to reconstruct the ways of penetration and spread of Christianity and Judaism in Central Arabia, where Islam was originally formed, then we can identify two main directions. The first way of their

penetration was from the south, through the ancient states and cities of Southern Arabia. It is known that in a certain, for a short period in the V century AD, Judaism was the state religion of the South Arabian Himyarite kingdom [15, p. 12]. At the same time, the traditional astral beliefs common in the more ancient states of Ma'in, Saba, Kataban and Hadhramaut continued to persist. But in 525, Ethiopian detachments led by Negus Ella Asbaha seized Southern Arabia, and later Abraham al-Ashram⁵, who ruled until 575, stood at the head of the Ethiopian warriors. According to Arab sources, he built a large Christian temple in Nejran and even set out to conquer Mecca and destroy the Kaaba, the oldest temple in Arabia. Abraha dreamed not only of turning the Arabs away from pilgrimage to this ancient shrine, but also of converting all of them into the bosom of the Christian church. The campaign to Mecca was unsuccessful for Abrahi, and in the Koran the whole Surah 105 is dedicated to this historical event:

"In the name of Allah, the Merciful, the Merciful!

1. Have you not seen what your Lord has done to the owners of the elephant?
2. Didn't He confuse their machinations
3. and did not send birds to them in flocks?
4. They threw stones of baked clay at them
5. and they turned them into the likeness of eaten withered grasses" [14, p. 607].

Commentary on the surah.

In accordance with the most authoritative comments of Ibn Qasir and al-Tabari, this surah refers to the campaign of Abrahi, who, intending to destroy the Kaaba, brought several elephants as part of his army. Since elephants were rare and unusual animals for the Bedouins, the whole army was called "elephant owners", and the lunar year in which this event took place (570-71 AD) was designated as the Year of the Elephant. According to legend, it was in this year, namely April 20, 571 A.D., that the prophet of Islam Muhammad was born [12, p. 19]. According to the commentaries, Allah sent flocks of birds to the army of Abrahi, who approached Mecca. They threw pieces of burnt clay at the soldiers, which caused a terrible disease from which many died. Modern commentaries suggest that the army was struck by a smallpox epidemic, as a result of which the campaign failed.

According to the data given in Arabic sources, which are largely confirmed by the latest works of Western researchers, the Christian doctrine of the Monophysite Tolk came to the south of Arabia together with the conquerors from Ethiopia, which proclaimed that the nature of Jesus Christ is only one, divine. This statement is confirmed by the Orthodox "Acts of the Apostles": "Already in the IV century Christianity seems to be established in Ethiopia or Abyssinia." The same source confirms that it was Monophysite Christianity that was widespread in Ethiopia: "Thus, the current Abyssinia owes its Christian enlightenment to Monophysite missionaries, therefore, Christianity was born here in the form of Monophysite" [8]. From this it can be concluded that it was this Christian sense

that spread in Central Arabia from the southern direction.

As for the northern direction, here the spread of Christianity among the Arabs went through the tribes of the Lakhmids, who founded their capital Hira (or Hirta) in the lower reaches of the Euphrates in the second half of the IV century. The Lakhmids initially served the Byzantines and, most likely, most of them professed Eastern or Orthodox Christianity, but then switched to the service of the Iranians, who supported the Nestorian trend of Christianity, which was persecuted in Byzantium, and accordingly many of the Lakhmids turned to this Christian trend.

As for the Ghassanids, they came to the northern borders of Byzantium later, already in the fifth century, and replaced the ancient Arab tribe of Salih as allies of the Byzantine-Tsev-philarchs. Many Ghassanids adopted Monophysite Christianity because they were in the service of the exarch of Antioch, who adhered to the Monophysite doctrine.

It is obvious that the ideas of Christianity spread in the northern part of Arabia precisely through the Lakhmid and Ghassanid kingdoms, which were respectively in the sphere of influence of Sasanian Iran and Byzantium, and in their religious preferences the Lakhmids adhered to the views of Nestorians, and the Ghassanids – Monophysites.

The differences between Monophysitism and Nestorianism in modern reference books are defined as follows. The essence of monophysitism lies in the belief that "the nature of Jesus Christ is divine, despite the fact that he possessed a human body during his earthly life. Thus, the teaching of the Monophysites proclaims that the nature of Jesus Christ is only one, divine, and not dual, earthly and human, as was confirmed at the Council in Chalcedon in 451" [5, p. 455]. Nestorian teaching recognized these two hypostases in Christ as separate, and they actually represented two separate personalities.

Based on these premises, it can be assumed that the attitude of Islam to Christianity, as set out in the Koran and the Sunnah, does not affect the main directions of Christianity - Orthodox and Catholic, which were finally divided only in 1054, and corresponds to the ideas of Arab nomadic tribes only about Monophysite and Nestorian interpretations. The knowledge about Christianity of the Prophet of Islam Muhammad himself, who, as is known, was an illiterate man, could be limited to only two of the above-mentioned interpretations of Christian teaching. The adherents of the mentioned Christian beliefs themselves were persecuted by the official clergy and the authorities of Byzantium in the V-VI centuries. In the 3rd verse of the 98th Sura of the Quran, it is explicitly stated that there are various interpretations among the "people of the Scripture", first of all, obviously, Christians: "Those who were given the Scripture fell apart after a clear sign appeared to them."

It follows from the above that the analysis of the provisions of the Koran and the Sunnah regarding Christianity should be carried out taking into account

⁵ The nickname al-ashram means "with a harelip" in Arabic.

that they reflect primarily the theological positions of the Monophysite and Nestorian interpretations, which can make a correlation in the assessment of the relationship between Islam and Christianity.

The spread of Judaism in Central Arabia also belongs to a rather late period. The rulers of the Himyarites, heirs of the ancient South Arabian civilization, adopted Judaism as the state religion only in the fifth century, and the compact settlement of Jews in South Arabia, according to the results of excavations by American and British archaeologists in the Aden area, is attributed to the second century [7, p. 52]. Connected with the world trade in incense, the aristocracy and the royal court of Himyar showed interest in biblical teachings, and some of them accepted Judaism, but there were much fewer Christians among the Himyarite rulers before 525, since Christianity was perceived as an instrument of Byzantine political expansion. In 525, Himyar was invaded by the Ethiopians, and the Himyarite king Yusuf Zu-Nuwas himself, who actively preached Judaism, died in battle, and the further spread of Judaism among the Arabs stopped. Despite all this, the Jewish tribes of South Arabia remained among the Yemeni Arabs until the 50s of the XX century, and the last Jews emigrated from Yemen to Israel only in the 70s.

The penetration of Judaism into Arabia from the north also began from ancient times. The Arabs themselves appeared on the borders of the Jewish state within Syria (ar. Sham) back in the IX century BC, and since that time historical sources in different languages constantly mention the Arabs. As for the presence of Jews in Northern Arabia, the beginning of their resettlement in this region is attributed to the period of the destruction of the second Jerusalem temple, i.e. after 70 AD. Their presence here confirms the presence of Jewish tombstones in the old parts of the cities located between Mecca and Palestine [7, p. 53]. It is quite obvious that the spread of Jews on the territory of the Arabian Peninsula is connected with the persecution of Jews by Roman troops.

If we compare the nature of the spread of Judaism and Christianity in the north of the Arabian Peninsula, it can be noted that Judaism came here together with the Jewish settlers, but remained only the religion of newcomers who did not engage in proselytism among the Arab tribes themselves. As for Christianity, the situation was reversed here. Christians spread their religion among all peoples in the most active way, as a result of which this religion was partially adopted by both South Arab and North Arab tribes. To date, there are no Christians left in the south of Arabia, since the Yemeni Arabs almost completely converted to Islam in the VII century as the new religion was strengthened, but in the north of the Arab East, in Syria, Lebanon, Palestine, Egypt, Christianity persists among the Arabs to this day.

Christian and religious studies literature often postulates the idea of the influence of Judaism and Christianity on the process of formation of the teachings of Islam, and sometimes it is argued that many texts and provisions of its main source - the Koran - are borrowed from Jewish and Christian sources. The claims that Muhammad was not a true prophet, and the Koran is just a "transcription" of the Old and New Testaments, borrowing religious ideas from Judaism and Christianity, go back in their roots to the writings of Christian polemicists of the early Middle Ages. At their head is John of Damascus, whose views on Islam will be discussed below. But until recently, a number of modern authors have reached absurd assumptions that there were some "mentors" from among Jews or Christians who allegedly taught Muhammad their religions. Sh. Goitein claims that Muhammad could get acquainted with biblical and apocryphal literature through Christian and Jewish channels [7, p. 57]. Even in some of the latest domestic textbooks on the history of the Arabs, it is claimed that "Muhammad combined knowledge about all monotheistic religions in his teaching, trying to apply them to the society in which he lived," collecting them during allegedly repeated conversations about religion "with representatives of various communities" [16, p. 17]. At the same time, it is completely silent that during the first caravan trip to Syria, Muhammad, where he was singled out from all the captains by the monk Bahira, was only 12 years old, and the meaning of what the Christian monk said to the head of the caravan and the boy's uncle Abu Talib was not to take the future prophet on future trips and to protect him from possible harm to him [12, p. 20]. And on the second trip to Syria with the caravan of his future wife Ha-didji bint Huweilid in 595, he was responsible for the success of this trade enterprise and provided a large profit to his mistress and future wife. Apparently, he did not have time to conduct religious conversations then. The Arab biographers of Muhammad do not talk about other allegedly "numerous" trips with caravans to Syria.

For a more thorough study of these issues, in our opinion, we should first turn to the facts from the biography of the Prophet of Islam Muhammad. Arab sources provide evidence that neither the contents of the Koran nor the Sunnah of the Prophet Muhammad were strongly influenced by Judaism or Christianity.

It is a reliable and universally recognized fact that Muhammad did not know how to read and write, did not know how to read and write. The Koran says about it: "You have not read any Scripture before and have not copied it with your right hand" (29:48)⁶. Accordingly, Muhammad could not know the contents of the Bible from written sources. In addition, it is hardly possible to assume such a wide spread of Jewish and Christian religious literature in the VII at the beginning of the century, not only in Mecca and Yasrib (Medina), but also in Arabia as a whole. Written monuments were a very rare phenomenon for the

⁶ The translation of the Koran is given according to Kuliyevev [14]. When referring to the Quran, the number before the colon indicates the number of the surah, and the numbers after the colon indicate the numbers of the verses.

culture of the central part of the Arabian Peninsula at that time, and manuscripts of religious content in Arabic or written in Arabic script could not exist due to the fact that a single language and its writing of the Arabs had not yet been formed by the beginning of the 7th century. Thus, it is hardly possible to assume that Muhammad and his companions could read the Bible or other religious writings.

There remains the possibility of using the means of oral communication and obtaining real information about the biblical history and the doctrine of Judaism and Christianity. As noted above, both Christianity and Judaism have spread to the periphery of the Arabian Peninsula, in the south and north. Muhammad, with the exception of two short trips with caravans to Syria in 582 and in 595, lived his entire life until the beginning of the discovery in 610 in the heart of the desert of Arabia, the city of Mecca, where there were no Jewish or Christian tribes and communities. There was nowhere for him to get information about the creed and sources of these religions in childhood and adolescence, when a person's worldview was being formed. In the biography of the Prophet compiled by Ibn Hisham, it is mentioned that the Christian monk Bahira saw the young teenager Muhammad during his journey with a caravan in Syria in the city of Busra and saw the seal of prophecy in him, ordering Muhammad's uncle Abu Talib to protect him especially zealously from the Jews and not to take him on trips [10, p. 64-67]. The legend itself is most likely not historical, but apologetic in nature, although it is considered reliable in Muslim literature. However, it would be groundless to claim that this meeting served as the basis for Muhammad's acquaintance with the dogmas of Christianity.

Another case of Muhammad's communication with Christians can be considered his conversation with Waraka ibn Naufal, who was a cousin of Khadija bint Huwaylid, the first wife of the Prophet Muhammad. Tradition reports that Waraka was familiar with Christianity, but he himself was a Hanif [13], i.e. one of those seekers of truth and unity of God who lived in various Arabian tribes, but did not adhere to any of the religions, as E.A. Rezvan characterizes Hanifov [17, p. 25].

According to Muslim sources, when the first revelation came, Muhammad expressed doubt about its divine origins, fearing that the phenomena come from evil spirits, jinns and shaitans. Then Khadija brought him to Warak, and he, having learned about the events that had taken place, reported that the Great Namus, the archangel Jibril, who came to Moses, appeared to Muhammad. Waraka confirmed that Muhammad would become a prophet of the new faith among the Arabs, but he himself soon died due to his venerable age.

This information is given in the most authoritative Muslim biographical work – Sire Ibn Hisham [10, pp. 92-93]. It no longer reports anything about Muhammad's communication with Christians and Jews before his relocation to Yathrib.

After the Hijra, the status of the Prophet Muhammad changed, and he became not only a

religious and spiritual leader, but also the head of all residents of the city of Yasrib (Medina), who, thanks to the adoption of Islam, began to feel like a single religious community, and it was she who later took shape in the first Muslim state education [3, p. 96]. As a judge, Muhammad was addressed not only by the Arabs of Yasrib (Medina) who had converted to Islam, but also by Jews and Christians who lived in the neighborhood of the city. Standing at the head of all the communities and tribes of Central Arabia and Yemen, the Prophet Muhammad, recognized by all, absolutely did not need theological recognition by either Jewish or Christian priests. It is difficult to assume that there were such wise "mentors" on the Arabian Peninsula who could teach religious issues to the head of all Arab tribes, who by that time had already firmly established himself as the universally recognized prophet of a new religion – Islam. Moreover, neither the Koran, nor the Sunnah, nor the Sira contain even hints of the possibility of Muhammad receiving instructions from Jews and Christians in Medina. And it is hardly possible to imagine that all these sources would simultaneously enter into a complete agreement not to mention any Jewish or Christian "mentors", if they really existed.

Nevertheless, the question remains: where could Muhammad get such extensive historical and religious information and transmit it in the form of a voluminous text of the Quran, which includes 77,845 words, comprising 6236 verses-ayats, combined into 114 chapters-surahs in pure Arabic?

The answer that Muslim theology gives to this question is that the Koran, and with it the rest of the texts of revelations sent down to the messengers of God, is the uncreated word of God (in Arabic, Allah), which was recorded in the heavenly archetype of all revelations – the Preserved Tablet. Thus, the coincidence of the Koran and the Bible is explained by Muslim theologians by the unity of the primary source from which all the prophets and messengers drew their knowledge. In the text of the Koran itself, this idea is emphasized repeatedly:

"Indeed, We have inspired you with a revelation, just as We inspired it to Nuh (Noah) and the prophets after him. We inspired the revelation to Ibrahim (Abraham), Ishmael (Ishmael), Isaac (Isaac), Jacob (Jacob) and the tribes (the twelve sons of Jacob), Isa (Jesus), Ayub (Job), Yunus (Jonah), Harun (Aaron), Suleiman (Solomon). To David (David) We gave Zabur (Psalter).

We have sent messengers that We have already told you about before, and messengers that We have not told you about. Allah had a conversation with Musa (Moses).

We sent messengers who brought good news and warned that after the coming of the Messengers, people would not have any argument against Allah. Allah is Mighty, Wise" (4:163-165).

To the opinions of Muslim theologians, we can add the statement that, without any doubt, there was a common Semitic tradition that contained Assyro-Babylonian, Aramaic, Jewish, Arabic elements, and all of them were reflected in the Babylonian cuneiform

inscriptions, in the Bible, and in the Koran. However, the Quranic transmission of this tradition did not receive the huge professional historical editorial revision that the biblical and evangelical texts in the person of Talmudists and evangelists underwent. From this it becomes clear why the Quran contains numerous stories, the names of prophets, peoples of the distant past, the names of localities found in the Bible, but at the same time the Quranic stories do not have a coherent narrative chronological line.

Nevertheless, the question of the origins, origin and formation of Islam continues to be relevant in modern Islamic and Oriental studies, since in Christian theology, in modern religious studies and in academic Oriental studies, an unambiguous attitude to Islam as a full-fledged and independent religion has not yet been definitively formed.

It is obvious that in the religious aspect, the question of the autochthonous nature of Islam as one of the world religions should be raised. The concept of autochthonous religion is defined as "religious beliefs and rituals that arose in an ethnic environment without external foreign religious influence and developed on the basis of cultural characteristics peculiar to an ethnic group; the primordial religion of the people" [18, p. 14]. The opposite of autochthonous religion is allochthonous religion, which is defined as "beliefs and rituals introduced into the religious life of the people from a foreign cultural environment; "foreign religion"" [18, p. 31].

Considering the problem of the autochthonous nature of Islam, it can be stated that the attitude towards Islam during a certain period of development of European theological thought, starting from the 8th century and up to the late Middle Ages, is generally defined as rejection of Islam as an independent and full-fledged religion. It was only with the advent of the Enlightenment that other points of view began to form in European thought regarding the primordial nature and originality of Islam as an independent religious teaching, but most often, when studying Islam, the main attention was focused on the coincidences of elements of the creed and cult of Islam and previous religions, namely Judaism and Christianity. Based on this, the concept was asserted that Islam is an allochthonous religion.

At the present stage of the development of religious and theological thought, three main positions can be distinguished:

- views of Christian theologians;
- views of religious scholars and orientalists;
- views of Muslim theologians.

The attitude of medieval Christian theologians-polemicists to Islam was formed at the beginning of the VIII century, and it is based on the extremely negative position of John of Damascus (675-750), set out in the 101st chapter of the book "On Heresies" [11]. The book was written, obviously, after 736, when John retired to a monastery, although before that he served at the court of the Umayyad Caliph Abd al-Malik ibn Marwan (646-705). The views of John of Damascus became fundamental for all other Christian polemicists until recently, although the controversy with Muslims was

expanded by later Byzantine and European theologians, in particular Theodore Abu Qurra (750-823), Nikita of Byzantium (IX century), Eulogius of Cordova (IX century), Peter of Cluny (XII century), Thomas Aquinas (XIII century.), Martin Luther (XVI century.) and many others. Let us briefly state the positions of Christian polemicists in relation to Islam:

1. Muhammad is not a true prophet (John of Damascus calls him

a "false prophet"), because he allegedly had no witnesses that God gave him the Scripture.

2. The Qur'an is neither the Word of God nor a Revelation, but a heresy composed by Muhammad due to "casual acquaintance with the Old and New Testaments."

3. The creed of Islam is false because it denies that God can have a son and that Jesus is God.

4. Professing Islam and observing its five pillars cannot provide salvation.

This remained the position of both the Catholic and Orthodox Churches until the second half of the XX century. Twelve centuries after the work of John of Damascus, the Catholic Church in 1965 adopted a declaration "On the attitude of the Church to non-Christian religions. *Nostra aetate*", which, in particular, says the following about Islam: "The Church also respects Muslims who worship the one God, living and existent, merciful and omnipotent, Creator of heaven and earth, who "spoke to people"... Despite the fact that for centuries there have been discord and enmity between Christians and Muslims more than once, the Holy Council calls on everyone to be forgotten the past and sincerely strive for mutual understanding, as well as to jointly protect and strengthen social justice, peace and freedom for all people" [22, p. 4-5]. This declaration declared that, despite the persistence of theological differences between Christianity and Islam, the attitude of the Catholic Church towards Islam has changed towards the recognition of Islam as the true religion.

This cannot be said about the position of the Russian Orthodox Church, since there is no document on changing its attitude to Islam, and modern Russian Orthodox polemicists in the person of Yu. Maximova, D. Sysoeva, R. Silantieva, A. Kuraeva persistently continue not to recognize Islam as the original religion.

Representatives of Western and Russian orientalism, defining their attitude to Islam, largely continued the line of Christian polemicists. They made their main conclusions in accordance with the ideological positions of Christianity, but added their own academic research. Since Europe's acquaintance with Islam was mainly through retellings and translations of the Koran into European languages, the interest of the first European orientalists was directed to the study of the text of the Koran. Philological, linguistic and textual studies of the Quran conducted in the XIX–XX centuries by G. Weil, A. Sprenger, V. Muir, G. Grimm, T. Neldeke, R. Bell, concentrated on finding parallels with biblical and other sacred texts, as well as on the arrangement of surahs and verses of the Quran in chronological order. Gradually, the attitude of European orientalists to the Koran as a "retelling of the

Bible" was transformed by the end of the XX century to recognize the Koran as an independent Holy Scripture of Islam. "Modern science practically does not raise the question of the authenticity of the Koran. The style of the individual parts of the Holy Book is different, but still it cannot be confused with anything else," writes the modern Islamic scholar U. Montgomery Watt [4, p. 65].

Similarly, the assessment of Muhammad's personality and prophetic activity in European orientalism transformed from the idea of Muhammad as a person possessed by the devil, then as a person seized by special mental states close to epilepsy. The doctor and arabist A. Sprenger was the first to try to prove this back in the XIX century, but since then many modern researchers of Islam have already been inclined to admit that Muhammad was the prophet of Islam, the Messenger of Allah and received divine revelation. They stopped following Christian polemicists who did not want to recognize Muhammad as a prophet of a new faith and religion. In particular, W.M. Watt recognizes the divine nature of the revelations given to Muhammad, although he stipulates that atheists represent this phenomenon as "intuitive creative imagination" [4, pp. 78-85, 112].

Russian Islamic studies mainly adhered to the views of Western orientalists on the Koran and the personality of Muhammad. At least until the end of the XIX century, Christian-theological or Western religious views prevailed in writings on Islam, as can be seen from the writings of A.E. Krymsky [15].

The Soviet period occupies a special place in the study of Islam in Russian science. On the one hand, there was an obvious militant atheistic propaganda, which was embodied in a number of works by Soviet researchers (L.I. Klimovich, E.A. Beryaev, etc.). It is curious that in one of his early articles in the spirit of militant atheism, L.I. Klimovich even questioned the reality of Muhammad's personality, imitating discussions about the historicity of Jesus. A striking example of a materialistic approach to the evaluation of Islam is the work of E.A. Belyaeva "Arabs, Islam and the Arab Caliphate in the Early Middle Ages", published in 1966. In it, the author presents Islam as the ideology of the commercial and feudal class of the Arab society of the VII century. Despite this, it can be noted that there were authors in Soviet Oriental studies who tried to maintain objectivity in relation to Islam. These include the historian V.V. Bartold, the Arabist I.Y. Krachkovsky, and others.

In the post-Soviet period, against the background of numerous translated religious literature about Islam, objective academic studies on the Koranic studies of E.A. Rezvan, D.V. Frolov and on the biography of Muhammad T.K. Ibrahim stand out. Relying mainly on Arabic sources, researchers present a Muslim view of the Koran and the personality of Muhammad, while maintaining non-religious neutrality.

The views of Islamic theology on the problem of the origins of Islam require a careful approach and a sufficiently deep independent study.

Both in Islam and Christianity, there is an idea that the truth of the prophetic mission must be confirmed or

certified in order for people to accept what is transmitted through him on faith. Such confirmations are understood primarily as miracles accompanying the prophet's activity, and prophecies in a narrow sense, i.e. predictions about future events [6, p. 5]. However, the main accusation of Muhammad of false prophethood in the work of John of Damascus, as can be seen from the above, is due to the absence of witnesses of revelation, which clearly indicates completely different approaches to the essence of the prophetic mission in Christianity and Islam.

Islam defines the concept of "prophecy" in accordance with its teaching, therefore, the Quran distinguishes two degrees of prophetic mission, which Allah bestows on selected people in order to convey religious precepts to people. These prescriptions are broadly defined in Islam by the concept of sharia. At the first stage are the prophets themselves, who in the Quran are designated by the word nabiy (mn. ch. anbiya, nabiyyun), and the very concept of "prophecy" is designated by the word nubuvva. In the text of the Quran, words from this root occur 80 times. According to the frequency of use, the word Nabiy is primarily addressed to Muhammad or is associated with the mention of him. This indicates that the Qur'an repeatedly confirms that Muhammad is a prophet, and for a Muslim, the testimony of the Qur'an is sufficient on any issue, since the Qur'an for him is the Word of God, in which there can be no deviations from the truth. To no lesser extent, the Quran speaks of other prophets. The text of the Quran mentions the names of only 25 prophets, starting with Adam and ending with Muhammad. At the same time, there is an opinion in Muslim theology that 124,000 prophets were sent to people. From the point of view of the Islamic creed, all these prophets are true and are revered as a chosen category of people who have been granted special mercy and knowledge from Allah.

At a higher level in the hierarchy of the prophets are the messengers of rasul (mn.ch. rusul), and the very concept of "messenger" in the Koran is designated by the word rizal. The word rasul is mentioned 336 times in the Quran, but rizal is mentioned only 10 times. It is quite obvious that such a frequency of mentioning these words indicates that the significance of the concept

The "messenger" in Muslim prophetology is significantly higher, and the fact that the word Rasul is mentioned in the earliest surahs according to the chronology of the revelation shows that in Islam the figure of the messenger is much more significant than the prophet. Already in the surahs of the first Meccan period, the word rasul is mentioned, while the word Nabiy is mentioned mainly in the surahs of the Medina period (according to the classification of T. Neldeke).

The problem of prophecy and messengers has become one of the central ones in Muslim dogmatics and theology. As you know, the first pillar (rukun) of Islam is the certificate of acceptance of Islam (shahada), which consists of two parts: la ilaha illa Llah; Muhammadun rasul Allah. These words translated into Russian mean:

"There is no god but Allah; Muhammad is the Messenger of Allah." Thus, for a Muslim, the first and

most important thing is to accept faith in the one and only God-Allah and that Muhammad is the Messenger of Allah. Similarly, in the Muslim creed, which lists six tenets of the creed, it is said about faith in messengers (rusul): "amantu biLlahi vama laikyatihi vakutubihi varusulihi val-yaum il-ahiri val-kadari hayrihi wa sharrihi min Alla-hi Ta'ala". By uttering these words, a Muslim asserts his faith in Allah, in angels, in the Scriptures, in messengers, in the future life and in predestination, the good and evil of which proceeds according to the will of the Almighty. The word rasul itself in Arabic is an adjective with a touch of the passive voice and is formed from the root rsl, which has the general meaning "to send, to send". From this, the translation into Russian of the word rasul is derived as "messenger, ambassador, messenger, apostle, harbinger" [2, p. 296].

However, the main thing in recognizing one or another religion as true, descending from heaven from God – ad-din as-Samawi, is the sending down of heavenly revelation to the prophet of this religion. In all the prophetic religions sent down from heaven, revelation is one of the most important postulates and the central concept of the creed, expressing the act of direct expression of the will of a personified God transcendent to the world, revealing himself as the absolute truth. The idea of revelation historically goes back to theistic teachings that admit the possibility of prophecies. In them, revelation is understood as the speaking of God through the mouth of a prophet or oracle, whose personality is displaced by supernatural forces at the moment of receiving the revelation. The primary concepts of revelation are defined in the ancient idealistic philosophy, in which the idea of being correlates with the real Absolute, which is not accessible to the senses and cognitive abilities of people. The absolute is different from the earthly realities available to cognition empirically through feelings and experience, and its supersensible nature requires completely different ways of cognition that go beyond the cosmic limits. Plotinus gave the most important impetus to the formation of ideas about revelation in ancient philosophy, who practically laid down all the fundamental criteria and characteristics of the later classical understanding of revelation for all theism:

- inner readiness to receive revelation (in Islam, this corresponds to the God-chosen istif);
- detachment, purification and elevation of the soul as its necessary prerequisites (cf. the concept of Isma in Islam);
- comprehension in the act of revelation of transcendent reality by direct perception of the absolute truth revealed by God (cf. wahy in Muslim theology);
- the non-reconstructibility of the Divine truth in a rational and logical way and by human efforts (cf. the postulate "ijaz al-Quran" in Islam);

For Muslims, the Quran is the Word of Allah, which was sent down to the Prophet Muhammad in various ways. Moreover, according to Islam, the Quran is not the only book of Allah sent down to people. The revelations were given to all the messengers before

Muhammad, but they were not preserved in their God-given form, but were distorted by people.

Thus, in accordance with the teachings of Islam, a true divine revelation was revealed to Muhammad, which was later collected in the holy book of Muslims – the Koran. The Quran appears as the last, final and perfect revelation of God, recorded in writing by human efforts in the form of Holy Scripture. The Quran is part of the Eternal Tablet kept by Allah, and was revealed to the Prophet Muhammad through revelation, which in the Quran is designated by the Arabic word wahy. This Arabic word translates as "suggestion, command, instruction", and the concept itself, expressed in the form of words of the same root with a similar meaning, is available in Aramaic, Hebrew, Ethiopian and other Semitic languages, which proves the existence of an original idea of revelation among all Semitic peoples. Initially, wahy could mean the instantaneous appearance of an image or idea in the prophet's mind, an order to inform other people about them, or to immediately perform a certain action. Words from this root occur 78 times in the Quran, but terminologically they denote phenomena of different order in the text of the Quran. With the formation of Muslim dogmatics, narrower concepts began to stand out from the undifferentiated Quranic concept of wahy. Thus, in Al-Tabari, when the term wahy is correlated with the prophets preceding Muhammad, it is interpreted as ilham – "inspiration". This idea was even more clearly formulated by Fakhr al-Din ar-Razi, giving the following classification:

- The wahy revealed to Muhammad is a "True revelation";
- wahy, revealed to other prophets, – ilham – "inspiration";
- Wahy, sent down to other people, angels, jinns, animals and even inanimate objects, is the "suggestion of instinct".

Summing up the results of this study, we can draw the following conclusions:

1. The attitude towards Islam as an allochthonous religion, which borrowed its ideas from other religious teachings, in particular Judaism and Christianity, has not passed the test of time and is an anachronism, which is adhered to in our time only by some representatives of theological and academic science.

2. Islam has all the elements inherent in the autochthonous world religious teachings, including revelation in the form of the Holy Scripture, the Koran, the holy tradition in the form of the prophetic Sunnah, the system of doctrine and religious cult, which have common elements with Judaism and Christianity, but not by borrowing, but by virtue of the unity of the divine source and the presence of a common Semitic spiritual legends.

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